

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

A high-purity gas-solid photoreactor for reliable and reproducible photocatalytic CO₂ reduction measurements

Nikolaos G. Moustakas, Marcus Klahn, Bastian T. Mei, Anna Pougin, Martin Dilla, Tim Peppel, Simon Ristig, Jennifer Strunk

Figure S1.: Photoreactor flow chart.

Figure S2.: Cross-section and dimensions (in mm) of a water saturator.

Figure S3.: Back-view of the water saturator with the four pipes used to supply (cooling) water (sides of the main body and the gas supply piping system (top side)).

Figure S4.: Angled front-view of the water saturator

Figure S5.: Top-view of the water saturator

Figure S6.: Detached gas-piping system and bubbler

Figure S7.: Top-view of the water saturator without the gas-piping system and bubbler

Figure S8.: Cross-section and dimensions of the main body of the reaction chamber

Figure S9.: Main body of the photoreactor with the lid attached.

Figure S10.: Main body of the photoreactor without the lid.

Figure S11.: Photoreactor lid (top side).

Figure S12.: Photoreactor lid (bottom side).